

Transformative Integration of Identity and Place: A Feminist Reading of *Jasmine* by Bharati Mukherjee

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15313498

*I have had a husband for each of the
women I have been. Prakash for Jasmine,
Taylor for Jase, Bud for Jane. Half-Face for Kali.
~Jasmine (Mukherjee)*

The academic discourse attributed to feminist criticism is both rich and revealing. With each new feminist reading, it becomes clear that we need to continue the discussions relevant to our gender. In a feminist critical analysis of Bharati Mukherjee's novel, *Jasmine*, there is much evidence of themes such as identity, naming and place. In this brilliant work of autobiographical fiction, or what many creative writers term as creative non-fiction, Mukherjee pulls the veil away from the face of her protagonist, Jasmine, and through the shifting identities of her character, we observe her as named by the men she becomes involved with throughout her quest for a true, single identity. Whether or not she finally attains this singular identity is vague, as the novel ends with her leaving to reassume one of the names given to her earlier in the journey.

Consequently, she becomes a mythological woman warrior, who has embarked upon a task that seems in some ways futile, and in others, necessary for re-writing the female body. Jasmine conquers the curse of an astrologer, the attack of a rabid beast, and the rape of a Cyclops figure. Like any true warrior, Jasmine defeats her enemies and, in the process, travels many miles across sea and land from India through Florida, New York, and Iowa. Her quest continues toward California, but we cannot be sure if she will settle there or continue her search for identity. The novel embodies the idea that "[t]he longing for a strong cultural identity has been an important desire and symptom of postcolonialism in the contemporary Indian context" (Kapur 87). We can then empathize with Jasmine as she travels through liminal spaces, hoping to fill in the gaps in her fragmented identity.

Therefore, what Bharati Mukherjeeⁱ accomplishes in this novel is two-fold: she sets the stage for discourse in feminine identity and the woman warrior; she also allows the reader to bridge the gap between what is real and what is imagined. "Clearly, the most important boundaries crossed have been those between fiction and non-fiction and—by extension—between art and life" (Hutcheon 206). As readers, we can identify with the truths and difficulties that life presents, as well as appreciate Jasmine's reality and the imagined liminal spaces she tries to fuse. The personal mythology that she creates is both figurative and literal, as she fights her way through trials that reserve for her the title of heroineⁱⁱ.

Jasmine does not enter the world as a heroine but instead is born a victim. For Jasmine, who was named Jyoti (Light) by her grandmother, life is anything but a ray of light as she constantly searches for a place of happiness. Throughout the novel, it seems she is caught between liminal binaries such as good/evil, security/poverty, stability/fragmentation, and Indian/American. Not only is she an "other" because of her gender and race, but she also is cursed by the village astrologer, who tells her she is marked for tragedy (Mukherjee 4-5).

It is this curse that incites her quest. Her journey will take her across continents and to America, as “[s]he must avoid the limiting boundaries that seek to confine her in traditional and specific gendered roles, both in India and America” (Ruppel). She is caught between names, identities, her native Hasnapuri, and later in America. As literary and cultural critic Homi Bhabha asserts:

The stairwell as liminal space, in-between the designations of identity, becomes the process of symbolic interaction, the connective tissue that constructs the difference between upper and lower, black and white. The hither and thitherⁱⁱⁱ of the stairwell, the temporal movement and passage that it allows, prevents identities at either end of it from settling into primordial polarities. (287)

This metaphor is essential in understanding how Jasmine is “displaced,” almost forced into the spaces between steps of the stairwell, unable to completely integrate herself into her native land or to assimilate completely into American life. The metaphor continues as we begin to recognize that Jasmine is consistently between names, as well as identities.

Jasmine’s identity is also challenged when the astrologer strikes her, causing her to fall and receive the star scar on her forehead, which she tells her sisters is her “third eye” and that she is now “a sage.” Even as a child, she begins to reinvent her destiny from starred/scarred/cursed to starred/sage/chosen (Mukherjee 3-5). In her culture, girls are curses: “Gods with infinite memories visited girl children on women who needed to be punished for sins committed in other incarnations” (39). Her very birth begins in victimization, as her mother attempts to strangle her to death. Her mother tried to choke her to death, fearing a cursed life for both of them. What seems to be an act of harsh mercy towards Jasmine is ultimately a disguised, selfish attempt to stamp out another mark on her reputation: that surely, she must have angered the gods in her previous lives to have birthed so many girl children (40-1). The words of the astrologer ring internally in Jasmine’s mind at each pivotal moment of turmoil in her life, as she hears “...foolish and wicked girl, did I not tell you you’d end up among aliens?” (203). The term *alien* ensures that she is viewed through a postcolonial lens—that she is in the margins and will continue to unsuccessfully search for a sense of her *place* in the world.

Even her father realizes that his daughter is not like other women, as he angrily beats his wife because she requests more schooling for Jyoti. When offered a position at a bank, she declines, saying to her Pitaji, “I want to be a doctor and set up my clinic in a big town” (51). She receives more schooling and learning some English, but like other girls her age, she hopes she can still marry without a dowry. She is forced into the liminal space within her own culture because she is female, and she is not a traditionally subservient one. According to Norman Holland, a Psychoanalytic critic, she is exhibiting an *identity theme*. “He [Holland] believes that in our daily lives, we project that identity theme onto every situation we encounter and thus perceive the world through the lens of our psychological experience” (as qtd. in Tyson 183). We have noted some of these identity themes in her early childhood; it is necessary to locate her identity themes in several other examples.

The first significant indication of her inner-goddess identity developing is her encounter as a young girl warrior. As she and the neighbourhood women spend their “Ladies’ Hour” bathing in the fields, a wretched and probably rabid dog scares all the women. Jyoti screams for help at the male voyeurs watching them bathe from afar, and they do not assist. The mystical quality of the dog-wolf is clear, as its “red eyes” search for prey, like the Cerberus of hell. Forced into a warrior status, Jyoti uses a staff to stab it. “The staff crushed the dog’s snout while it was still in mid-leap. Spiny twigs hooked deep into its

nostrils and split them open” (Mukherjee 55-7). Later in the novel, the narrator tells us, “[f]or every monster there is a hero. For every hero, a monster” (114). She kills her Cerberus; later she will kill her Cyclops.

Like a good warrior, she renegotiates her place or in-between space throughout the novel, adapting to the renaming of her identity by the men in her life. When she marries Prakash he changes her name from Jyoti to Jasmine, which she admits places her in an odd space, “shuttled between identities” (77). For this, she seems grateful, because she has been taken out of her oppression in Punjab and is encouraged to speak her mind. He even tells her to address him by his first name, which is normally a sign of disrespect. While he is progressive in his culture, he still makes many of her decisions, such as living outside of his uncle’s household. Jasmine feels as though she is “suspended between worlds” of Indian duty and progressive ideology (76). Jasmine understands fully the requirement of procreation prescribed by her culture. “Indeed, in this society, pregnancy is the only available identity” (Ruppel). As a result, when Prakash is bombed to death, she realizes that not only has she lost a man she has grown to love, but also, she has lost the potential to bear children, for widow-wives are forced to remain barren, never to remarry again in her culture. Thus, she attempts to recreate or redefine her space; this time she is in control and chooses to go to America. True, it was Prakash’s dream to go, but she chose to go alone.

Jasmine continues to go through the process of liminal identities when she reaches America and as such, “others” herself, as well as the men who rename her. “Hence, to be outside of purportedly divided and contained racial categories is to have no place—it is to lack (or defy) definition,” states Mary K. Bloodsworth-Lugo (5). This literary critic goes on to discuss that, “despite the liberating and resistant potential of in-between positions, to exist in-between extremes has nonetheless been difficult for individuals so ‘situated’”, such as Jasmine (5). She has learned to accept her liminal space as a wife, and now she will do so alone in America.

She is never more alone than when she first arrived in Florida. A key passage in the novel is the rape scene in which Jasmine is forced to have sex with Half-Face, a predator duly named for his deception in showing only half of his intentions toward Jasmine by “helping” her find a place to stay. This is her second encounter as a warrior, only this time she is a woman, not a young Indian girl. Half-Face is a kind of Cyclops with a “dead eye,” a mythological figure, whom she must kill (Mukherjee 108). After the violent rape, she kills him and wants to kill herself, since she sees her body as “merely the shell, soon to be discarded” (121). Once dead, she believes she can be “reborn” in the afterlife. It is significant that she slits her tongue before she kills Half-Face, because in this way, she cannot utter her name, nor does she care to identify with it. Jasmine had been a “purified” named by Prakash. Now the name is defiled by a man who is “evil” and from “the underworld” (116).

The ritual involved in the killing is symbolic of a warrior heading to battle. Jasmine must kill the second beast in her life for rebirth. Mukherjee describes the ritual in great detail as a flashback:

I determined to clean my body as it had never been cleaned, with the small wrapped bar of soap, and to purify my soul with all the prayers I could remember from my father’s and my husband’s cremations. This would be a fitting place to die. I had left my early body and would soon be joining their souls...I reached into the pocket of my salwar for Kingsland’s [fellow traveler] knife. Until the moment I held its short, sharp blade to my throat I had not thought of any conclusion but the obvious one: to balance my defilement with

my death...I could not see, as I had wanted to, the arm reaching to the neck, the swift slice, the end of my mission...[which was not yet over]. I didn't feel the passionate embrace of Lord Yama...[and] I had not yet burned my husband's suit. (Mukherjee 117-8)

After purifying her body, and killing her Cyclops, she proceeds with burning her husband's suit. The symbolic slitting of her tongue serves as a kind of self-mutilation, much like that of other warriors throughout history who have cut, branded, burned, or tattooed themselves before going to war to defeat their enemies. As she lets the blood drip out of her mouth, presumably onto his body, she stabs him. After burning Prakash's defiled suit (since Half-Face had touched it) in the make-shift funeral pyre and chanting her "prayers for the dead," she sets out to complete the rest of her suicide mission in Tampa, where Prakash had intended to complete his mission: education (118-121). In this symbolic journey, she hopes to be reunited with him in rebirth.

She becomes a goddess, Kali, as she has killed her enemies and claimed her status among other women warriors. "In Hinduism, the 'kali-yuga' is the final stage of existence before annihilation whereupon the cycle repeats itself" (Roberts 89). She redeems her suit-burning ritual by following the killing with a makeshift funeral pyre. Then, like a lone warrior making her way home, she "travels light" as she continues her quest. Her journey becomes even more epic, for she has faced the "Cyclops," made her sacrificial offering, and continues her journey towards an identity.

Thankfully, she meets Lillian Gordon on this road, who becomes her saviour, and who does not prod her about who she is, or what has happened to her, but instead introduces herself. Lillian remarks, "I won't ask yours [name] because it's probably a fake. This I take it—she was feeling [Jasmine's] kameeze—isn't Guatemalan, is it? Are we talking India here? Punjab? Are you Sikh?" (130). Because of her experiences in assisting undocumented immigrants in the States, she can guess where Jasmine has come from and to assist her. Lillian renames her "Jazzy" (133). Lillian gives "Jazzy" a room of her own^{iv}, her daughter Kate's room, where she can develop a new American identity. The next few weeks become private tutoring sessions of American cooking, cleaning, and of course, "passing" though still an *alien* in public places. She tells Jazzy, "[n]ow remember, if you walk and talk American, they'll think you were born here" (134-5). Without proper papers, this is the only way for Jazzy to become acculturated, by "passing" as American-born. She is placed once again in a liminal space between identities and ethnicities.

As if parallel to her identity changes, later in the novel an interesting change in naming takes place at the Flamingo Court, where Jasmine had been raped. The place was purchased, transformed, and renamed the Paradise Bay Complex (138). Even though the space is transformed, the memory that Jasmine associates with it has not; it is still the run-down, filthy prison where she was first introduced to "Americana." What is especially relevant is that for Jasmine, this place is one of her battlegrounds—a place of personal war.

As she progresses further into her identity, we realize this will be an evolutionary process, one in which she must continue to reinvent herself. Homi Bhabha has noted, that not only must she do so internally, but she also must continue merging herself into her surroundings, as "[t]he borderline work of culture demands an encounter with 'newness' that is not part of the continuum of past and present" (290). The temporality and spatiality that Jasmine inhabits "...renews the past, refiguring it as a contingent 'in-between' space, which innovates and interrupts the performance of the present. The 'past-present' becomes part of the necessity, not the nostalgia, of living" (209). This dilemma will continue as she decides

to go to Flushing, New York where she knows there is an Indian family willing to assist in her journey.

In Flushing, she is expected to play the role of the widow and stay with her host family for five months. The Vadheras welcome her, but she never feels like she is home or has found her *place*. Perhaps the renaming of her host, Professorji, contributes to her confusion about the identity of an Indian American. “He ha[s] a new name in New York. Here he [is] ‘Dave,’ not Devinder...” (Mukherjee 143). While he is busy “passing” as American, Jasmine is Americanized in her pants and t-shirts. She is asked to wear traditional Indian mourning clothes instead. Even her clothing renames her:

I could not admit that I had accustomed myself to American clothes. American clothes disguised my widowhood...In this apartment of artificially maintained Indianness, I wanted to distance myself from everything Indian, everything Jyoti-like...Flushing was a neighborhood in Julundhar. I was spiraling into depression behind the fortress of Punjabiness.^v (145; 148)

She feels a strange sensation of being “othered” as Indian and American, woman and widow. She realizes that she must leave their home if she is ever to find her true identity. She decides to move out of this liminal space of daughter-widow and into another, that of a displaced, undocumented Indian American.

A seemingly insignificant passage in the novel deals with Jasmine’s first meeting with Kate, Lillian’s daughter, and her pet iguana. Kate is fascinated with Jasmine, and begins taking photographs of her, which seems like a form of exoticism. Another exotic element in Kate’s life is her pet iguana, Sam. Jasmine has an aversion to certain animals, obviously because of her traumatic encounter with the Cerberus creature in the desert. She feels differently about this animal though, almost as though they were two like beings. She thinks to herself, “[t]ruly, I had been reborn...I looked into his beady little eyes, his ugly wattled face. Sam...we’re both a long way from home, aren’t we?” (163-6). She realizes then that there is “no going back” to her homeland (164). She is in another liminal space: between the immediate home or the rootedness of an eventual home and the end of her journey.

Jase becomes her shortened name when she enters Wylie’s, Taylor’s, and Duff’s lives. Here, she notes she has become “an American” (165). Thankfully, Kate sets up this job so that Jasmine can assimilate even more into the American lifestyle. Like the other men in her life, Taylor renames her, but she likes it, as she admits, “I liked the name he gave me: Jase. Jase was a woman who bought herself spangled heels and silk chartreuse pants” (176). She realizes that she is in love with him and doesn’t mind the frivolous nickname he has given her, because it makes her feel adventurous, like a woman warrior. In this same chapter, we learn that she is beginning to understand her various identities: “...Jyoti was now a sati-goddess^{vi}...[and] Jasmine lived for the future...[while] Jase went to movies and lived for today” (176). Ironically, Taylor tells her he will become “homeless” for her, allowing her to use his study as her bedroom. Certainly, he does not understand the true meaning of what it is for an Indian woman without papers to be “unhomed” (172). However, we cannot fault his quip, since we see that in the grand scheme, he does understand her and grows to love her in his way.

Wylie, who also grows to love her, calls her both a sister and her “caregiver,” which allows Jase to feel like a professional American woman with a vocation, and also renames her. However, the name she seems to enjoy the most is “day mummy,” which is what Duff named her. This name causes some tension between Wylie and Jasmine, but the name is even more symbolic than the child could have known. For Jasmine, who had wanted a child,

this may be her only opportunity to have one, because she knows she cannot have a widow-marriage or her children. Yet, she desires children. Literary Critic Julia Kristeva in her response to Freud's work describes this desire in "Women's Time," as follows:

Pregnancy seems to be experienced as the radical ordeal of the splitting of the subject: redoubling up of the body, separation and coexistence of the self and of an other, of nature and consciousness, of physiology and speech.^{vii} This fundamental challenge to identity is then accompanied by a fantasy of totality—narcissistic completeness—a sort of instituted, socialized, natural psychosis" (Richter 1576)^{viii}.

Later, when Jasmine becomes pregnant, we are left to wonder whether the new child will enhance or fragment her identity further. Readers may recall how Jyoti was born into the world, nearly strangled to death.

Jasmine continues to live with Taylor and Duff after Wylie leaves to engage in an extramarital affair. We readers cannot completely fault Wylie for leaving, because she senses the growing affection between *Jase* and Taylor, and she is just as empty there as Jasmine will be later in the novel as Bud's Jane. She asks Jasmine, "I've got to go for it, right?" (Mukherjee 181). While she is "happy" with her life, Wylie still feels as though something is missing. For Jasmine, this opens a familiar liminal space even wider, as she thought she finally had her family—regardless of her widow status. She fears the disintegration of this family, and creates a new family, even encouraged by Wylie, who loves her like a sister and hopes for Taylor's happiness. In comparison to the other day's mummies in the building, Jasmine feels fortunate and even becomes more "rooted" in her new American persona (179). She falls deeply in love with Taylor because even though he has renamed her, he does not want to "change" her by "sanitiz[ing]" her alien identity (185). In this way, she becomes more "Jase" and not "Jasmine." She understands, though, that she will continue to remake herself, that as Kristin Carter-Sanborn asserts, she will "murder who [she was] so [she] can rebirth [herself] in the images of dreams" (577).

Conversely, when she leaves New York abruptly, it is to protect Taylor and Duff, not because she is seeking a new identity. She is terrified that they will be harmed or even killed by Sukkhi Sukhwinder, who had been responsible for the bomb that killed Prakash. She immediately sees Sukkhi, who recognizes her while she is at the park with Taylor and Duff, and fears that he may know she is illegally in the States. Therefore, she chooses to selflessly leave the family she loves. Taylor begs her to stay, saying, "you belong here," but she knows at that moment she no longer belongs (Mukherjee 6). She understands that she must leave and that she is no longer "home." We look to Cixous' "Laugh of the Medusa" for another metaphor that best describes Jasmine's decision: "Flying is woman's gesture...for centuries we've been able to possess anything only by flying; we've lived in flight, stealing away, finding, when desired, narrow passageways, hidden crossovers" (27-8). In this way, she is fulfilling the plight of all oppressed women; she is learning how to fly within/out of her body, and she understands that escapism is her only hope if she is to be reborn repeatedly. Ultimately, though, she is doing this for Taylor and Duff because she genuinely does grow to love them as family.

As she makes her way to Iowa, she meets the next man who will name her. Bud, who leaves his wife Karin, calls her Jane. We consider Bud's name inverted, which is "dub." One wonders if there is any hidden agenda in using Bud as the character's name because it denotes "dub," which is to name informally. Or did Mukherjee simply choose the name based on other reasons? Either way, Jasmine's relationship with Bud is much like that of the exotic

to the imperialist, capitalist (banker), who falls in love with the mystery of “otherness.” It is in this space of Baden, Iowa, that Jane finds another family, another one that she creates. However, unlike her relationship with Wylie and Taylor, she comes in like a storm, or what Karin calls, “the tornado” (205). Their separation is Wylie’s doing; whereas Jasmine seems to undo Karin and Bud Ripplemeyer, who had two grown children. She may not have pursued Bud, but he instantly falls for her beauty the minute Mother Ripplemeyer introduces her as a potential employee. Just as Bud erases Karin from his life, Karin symbolically erases Jane as she admits: “I wrote your name on a piece of paper. Then I lit it with a match” (202). As if able to walk through the fire, this woman warrior, now Jane, seems unaffected by this confession.

Once the warriors integrate, Jase’s identity morphs into Jane’s, and the space she negotiates in the home they live in, which is characteristically smaller and less attractive than the one Bud had built for Karin, becomes another liminal space for Jasmine to dwell. Karin receives the big, lonely house in the divorce; Jane receives Bud and his offspring, and eventually, his paralyzed body. Both women lose in this deal. Bud received twenty-eight years of Karin’s life; Jane receives several years of “happy enough,” as she indicates her home complete with cosy “add-ons.” She feels as though she is integrated into this new family, regardless of Karin’s harassment, and begins “thinking that all of us Ripplemeyers, even us new ones, belong” (Mukherjee 13). Yet, she and Bud’s adopted Vietnamese son, Du, never quite feel as though they *completely* belong. For Jane, she belongs as much as she dares to; Du remains guarded, even deserting them to find his biological sister in California, who keeps him alive in the refugee camps.

When forced to survive through constant displacement, Du becomes distrusting of “rootedness,” because “place” means in transit for him, not in stagnation. Yet this teenager is older than his years, as he perceives the postcard, she receives from Taylor has some kind of pull, as he tells her that the photograph on the card is of “[a] revolutionary’s wife who ended up living among strangers” (210). It is hard to imagine that Du will ever feel completely at home—even with his blood relative—because he will never forget what it feels like to be a stranger in a strange land. The reader may wonder if this is what will happen to Jane, too. Will she continue living her life as a transient, fragmented woman?

The use of flashbacks/forwards assists in relaying the fragmentation of her identity. In this sense, the novel is a postmodern feminist text, and she is constantly being rewritten and renamed. It takes great mastery to fuse these fragments to create a complete depiction of the life of an individual character. Even viewing Jasmine through the eyes of these men (and in some cases women) assists in how we grasp her chameleon identity. In the end, it seems she finally does find her true name. She seems to be quite comfortable with Jase as she realizes she “stopped thinking of [her]self as Jane” (240). The reader is left to wonder if she will settle on the Jase identity for good.

Additionally, prominent feminist critic, Helene Cixous, encourages a woman to “write [her]self,” and this is exactly what Jasmine performs throughout the novel (25). Yet, we are left with many questions. As Taylor and Duff arrive in Iowa to take back “Jase,” we wonder what is waiting for her in California. It is the land of the Gold Rush, where she will finally complete the jigsaw identity of her life and reconnect with Du. She understands what it is to be an Indian American woman warrior who has finally found herself and completed her quest. Presumably, she will become more rooted with Taylor and Duff. When considering whether or not Jasmine is selfish for leaving Bud, we can consider that, “[l]eaving, which occupies the concluding space of marriage, identifies the ending as a choice between being a

victim and being a victimizer while it also evades that choice; Jasmine could as easily be the latter as the former, it suggests bravely, but it's better to be neither" (Robbins). This is the liminal space: she is neither wife nor mistress.

She chooses to stay in between these social stations, even though there are dangerous (and sometimes murderous) consequences. She seems most "complete" in identity when she is couched "in-between" other already established family structures. She fits nicely into the open, liminal cracks of their lives, and in doing so, eventually finds that it is too crowded there after all. "The ways in which Jasmine moves between the metaphorical violence of identity transformation, the notion of representation itself as violence, and the fact of empirical violence raise a number of theoretical and methodological difficulties" (Carter-Sanborn 583-4). We hope that her journey continues in California and that she will find a place to "root" herself, if not for her sake, then for the sake of her unborn child. Whether Jyoti, Jasmine, Jase, Jane, or Kali, our woman warrior has many battle wounds to prove her bravery—including her first wound, the star on her forehead. At the end of the novel when Taylor and Duff retrieve "Jase" and take her to California, we peer out the window, watch them drive down the rugged road and imagine her clicking the seatbelt over her swollen belly, our woman warrior.

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Author (s) Contribution Statement: Nil

Author (s) Acknowledgement: Nil

Author (s) Declaration: I declare that there is no competing interest in the content and authorship of this scholarly work.

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Notes

ⁱ Stephen Fredman's anthology, *A Concise Companion to Twentieth-Century American Poetry*, includes an interesting feminism critical essay entitled, "Feminism and the Female Poet" by Lynn Keller and Cristanne Miller. In this essay, the authors note that, "Some feminist poets advanced women's liberation by exploring such taboo subjects as menstruation, female eroticism, childbirth, incest, or rape. Others reconstructed lost histories—whether individual women, of matriarchal societies, or, especially for ethnic minorities, of partially lost traditions" (89). Although their analysis is aimed at poetry, I find Mukherjee's novel especially relevant in dealing with most of said issues. Her work is prolific, pointed, and passionate. She dares to deal with taboo subjects, while attempting to reconstruct a female protagonist's fragmented identity.

ⁱⁱ Incidentally, Kate, Lillian's daughter helps Jasmine find the caregiver position for Wyle and Taylor and calls her leaving Flushing "heroic" (Mukherjee 161). This refers back to my idea that Jasmine is a heroic woman warrior.

ⁱⁱⁱ Some terminology and/or concepts derived from Pascal-Yan Sayegh's *Cultural Hybridity and Modern Binaries: Overcoming the Opposition Between Identity and Otherness*.

^{iv} Refers to Virginia Woolf's text *A Room of One's Own* (1929).

^v Raj, Akhila. Multiculturalist Aspect in Bharathi Mukherjee's Jasmine and Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's arranged marriage. January 2021 [International Journal of English Literature and Social Sciences](https://www.ijels.com) 6(3):322-325. DOI:[10.22161/ijels.63.45](https://doi.org/10.22161/ijels.63.45)

^{vi} The goddess is named Kali. As noted by Rajeswari Sunder Rajan in *Real & Imagined Women: Gender, Culture and Postcolonialism*, "The embodiment of authority in a female figure is one of the ways in which power is gendered female...In India the most facile investment of power in the female is through the concept and the embodiment of the goddess as 'Shakti', 'Durga', or 'Kali' (114). In so performing this warrior-goddess ritual, Jasmine has become Kali, who empowers her to commit the act and follow through with the funeral rites of her murdered husband, Parkash. The act of suicide after the funeral rites in which a woman throws herself on the pyre is called "sati" and has been the source of much debate in women's activist groups all over India (59).

^{vii} Some terminology and/or concepts derived from "Cherríe Moraga - Norma Alarcón (essay date 1988)." *Drama Criticism*, edited by Timothy J. Sisler, Vol. 22. Gale Cengage, 2004, 11 Feb. 2025 <https://www.enotes.com/topics/cherrie-moraga/criticism/moraga-cherrie-77981/criticism-giving-up-ghost/norma-alarcon-essay-date-1988>